

Theatrical Exposition of Religion and the Challenge to National Unity in Nigeria

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Abstract

The growing spate of retrogression into atavistic tendencies in human relations despite advancements in technology and enlightenment in all frontiers of existence points to the fact that things are not as they appear or look, and latent motives seem to overshadow man's manifest interactions. This paper discusses a perspective on religion that has increasingly become a divisive rather than a unifying force vis-à-vis the state of affairs in the nation. This sacred institution's drama has made it difficult for it to fulfil its true mandate in the lives of its followers, particularly in terms of fostering social unity. Religion has become the stimulus for all forms of atrocities and the melting pot of all drama ensuing in the nation's socio-political milieu. Surely, dialogue must go beyond the directors (leaders) and engage the actors (followers) in the search for common ground.

Keywords: Religion, leaders, followers, drama and national unity

Introduction

A potpourri of cultural and ethnic diversity, which if harnessed appropriately could be a source of human and material wealth, is the lament of many concerning Nigeria. Yet, this same geographical entity has become home to all sorts of aberrations in human relations as well as activities in key institutions. Religion has become the ticket to inclusion or exclusion from any socio-political or economic appointment or gain. Religion has assumed a sub-structural character, defining what happens in other institutions like politics, government, education, and law, as well as recruitment into or dismissal from public corporations. The word "religion," though lacks a universally accepted definition, is very relevant to man's life in this world and the next. The word comes from the Latin word "*ligare*," which means to join or link, and was classically understood to mean the linking of human and divine. It thus denotes a connection or relationship between man and a being greater than man. Humans and religion are inseparable in all human cultures.¹ Religion represents a kind of binding force and also a sanitizing agent for the naturally irrational tendencies of man, visible in the forms of segregation and inequalities that characterize all human societies. Religion means adherence to a set of beliefs or teachings about the deepest and most elusive of life's mysteries,² "a belief in divine (superhuman or supernatural) being(s) and the practices (rituals) and the moral code (ethics) that result from that belief." The tenets are what give religion its "thought," the rites its "form," and the ethics its "heart."³

Religion has also been defined as "a set of sacred and deep in rational scrutiny beliefs and practices based on faith." Therefore, it can quite easily trigger emotional reactions⁴. Bearing in mind Jonah Elaigwu's view of religion, one can understand how emotions easily set in at the mention of the word "religion." To Chukwuka Achunike religion is "man's awareness and recognition of his dependent relationship on a transcendent being—the wholly other, expressible in human society through beliefs, worships, and ethical and moral behaviors."⁵

Because beliefs and moral codes of conduct are important aspects of religion, it goes without saying that custodians of such beliefs and codes hold a revered position akin to that of the supernatural or spiritual being(s) and also have some powers to punish erring members. The sanctity of religious beliefs and values also confers on the followers a sense of devotion and psyche that should distinguish them from non-followers in their actions and

words. However, religious groups in Nigeria appear to play a double game in which acts performed in places of devotion or worship are sacred while behaviours performed outside of places of devotion or worship conform to worldly expectations and dictums. Herein lies the greatest dilemma facing mankind: the discordance between words and actions, between saying and doing, between preaching and practicing. Perhaps man is innately a *dramatis personae* in all facets of his existence.

Over the years, religion has assumed a fluid dimension in Nigeria's socio-political milieu. In times of calm, religious sermons take pride in the moment, quoting verses from holy books to support the perpetuation of the peace. In political affairs, religious leaders—particularly prominent ones—become professional seers, making proclamations, unveiling visions, and openly supporting aspirants and declaring winners before polls are conducted.⁶ These leaders also speak authoritatively about the divinity of their preferred candidate or the person's divinely ordained role in the prosperity of adherents during the anticipated political dispensation. Thus, followers are caught up in performances that show support for or dislike of a particular candidate based on the leader's "spiritual guidance." Hence, the easiest and fastest way to create disharmony among interacting individuals is to interpret any social phenomenon through religious lenses—kind words automatically transform into nasty ones, and both sides become highly vindictive.

Theoretical Framework

Dramaturgy is a micro-level approach to understanding people in the context of their daily interactions and behaviors. From the smallest unit to the larger groups in society, the daily behaviours of people are coded in symbols that represent the groups or society's ideas, thoughts, values, and beliefs. These symbols have meanings attached to them that are understood by all members of the same group and society. These symbols can be physical objects, gestures, non-verbal communications, pictures, and much more. Hence, a symbol with a meaning attached dictates the behaviour of individuals, and in fact, symbols are a part of information control.⁷

As an offspring of symbolic interactionism, dramaturgy presents a perspective for understanding behaviour using the theatrical scenario. Erving Goffman (1922-1982) proposed dramaturgy, also known as dramaturgical approach or dramaturgical analysis, with early inspiration traced to the great English playwright William Shakespeare's motto for the famous Globe Theater in London, written in Latin as *Totus mundus agit histrionem* "All the world's a stage, and all men and women are merely players."⁸

Dramaturgy analogizes human behaviour and interaction with theatrical production, where society is viewed as a stage and social life is regarded as "performance" carried out by "actors"—individuals and groups. Like in a theatrical production, life consists of two sides: "the front stage" and "backstage." Front-stage behaviour refers to our actions or behaviours when we are aware that others are watching us while the backstage represents behaviour displayed when no one is watching. It also features a different set of rules and customs from what is expected on the front stage. Emphasized within this perspective is the importance of "setting" or "context" in shaping the performances of actors. The timing and place where social interaction occurs, as well as the audience present to witness the "act," are all crucial to the performance of actors. Thus, when a performance typically reserved for one area makes its way into another, confusion, controversy, embarrassment, distrust, etc. are liable to ensue.⁹

Dramaturgy is also centered on the creation, maintenance, and destruction of a common understanding of reality by people operating individually and collectively to present a shared and unified image of reality. The self, which is central to this analysis and the interactionist perspective as a whole, is thought to be a vessel through which group ideals are imprinted and displayed. These groups (teams) on which an individual relies to promote or refute a given definition of the situation are responsible for the formation of impressions or perceptions of reality in social settings.¹⁰ As people present themselves in everyday life, playing roles on the front and backstage, there is always that drive to present the "self" and behaviour in the best way possible in order to maintain certain impressions of themselves to various audiences while in interaction.¹¹

Sign vehicles such as appearance, costumes, settings, gestures, voice, and postures are employed to skillfully manage performances (behaviours) in such a way that presents a favourable public image of the actor.¹² More so, people tend to be sensitive to how they are perceived by others. To this extent, therefore, man is considered a "big con"—to conceal information is deliberate, and to deceive is a common feature of our daily lives.¹³ Ashley Norris notes that values, roles, norms, and statuses are hardly ever passed on to us in their pure form, nor do we accept them mechanically; rather, we mould them in a way that suits our interaction with others. This game of presenting the self in the best way possible to influence the perception of others about the self is known as "impression management," and whether an individual engages in this process consciously or not, one cannot completely deny the fact that the acclamation of human behaviour as complex is rooted in the tenets of dramaturgy.¹⁴ A dramatic approach can be applied to understand behaviour in various spheres of human interaction and endeavor such as, worlds of airline flight attendants, employees at Disney stores and other service-oriented enterprises, insurance salespeople, automobile salespeople, employer employee relations, social interactions among colleagues/peers, political spheres etc.

In Nigeria's social and political milieu, dramaturgy has been employed to depict the drama that ensues between protagonists and antagonists in their competition to affect or win the audience (population/masses). It is common practice for politicians seeking votes from electorates to present their front selves on the political stage, professing exciting manifestoes and promises that toy with the psyche of their supporters and the larger audience. Whereas the backstage selves of the political aspirants are greed, parochialism, corruption, and all the opposites of the front stage selves. The protagonists or directors keep convincing the audience (the electorate) that their votes are secure, the process is transparent with public display of counting at selected polling units, and the trending charade of electronic voting/card reader purported to beat all forms of manipulation.¹⁵

In unionism at the student and national levels, the same drama plays out with union leaders who mobilise workers for strike actions and go back to re-negotiate agreements with management while unsuspecting workers are advised to return to work in the hope that their demands will be addressed.¹⁶ The current events in Nigeria's religious circles necessitate theatrical contextualization, as seen in the leaders-followers relationship. Unlike in reality, where the script writers are physically present, the grand scripts (the holy books of various faiths) are held to have been handed down by supreme, immortal beings who control the affairs of human beings through convictions that are sometimes not amenable to logical reasoning. Perhaps this forms the basis of the powers exercised by religious leaders who are the directors of religious performances.

As in a play, religious leaders assume superior knowledge of the grand scripts (Bible, Quran). They digest the scripts and deduce their meanings, which are fed to the audience (followers) via regular sermons, audio and print media, and in interactions outside the stage (at a church, mosque, or any other sacred place). Some followers hold on to their leaders' teachings so tenaciously that any attempt to downplay the spiritual authority of the latter is greeted with a militant response. Apart from devotion to spiritual heads, a certain degree of "brainwashing" is likely applied to ensure unflinching devotion to the creed and reduce the rate of breakaways.

When on stage, religious leaders extol the virtues of "brother's keeper," "good neighborliness," tolerance for non-adherents of one's faith," and so many other sweet lines that capture the hearts of the audience. But as soon as an event that should be considered inevitable occurs, the reaction is far from portraying anything close to the virtues showcased to the public. So, what should we say about religion in Nigeria? Have directors lost command of their actors? Have actors grown so independent that they can perform without proper scrutiny by directors?

Religion and Its Pivotal Role in National Affairs

In many parts of the world, religion provides people with social cohesion and strong feelings of belonging to adherents that solidify shared identities¹⁷. However, the pluralistic nature of Nigeria makes this virtue unrealizable. The religious institution in Nigeria has gained prominence as a catalyst for changes in political, social, economic, and legal institutions in Nigeria. The Nigerian populace easily identifies religious underpinnings

to actions and sensitive national decisions that are sometimes capable of disrupting the already fragile frame of the nation. Religion is concerned with providing meaning to the inevitabilities, frustrations, and contradictions of social life as well as controlling anxieties and tensions that could be disruptive, capture the role of religion in promoting stability and sanity in the individuals that make up society.¹⁸ This represents the ideal place of religion in human society as contained in the original scripts that serve as instruction manuals for various faiths. As part of its social control function, religious beliefs, norms, and values are expected to direct the activities of men in such a way that the secular sphere of life would experience the touch of true meaning derivable only from connection to the supernatural.

Sadly, religion in Nigeria has derailed from its role of stabilizing actors in the social system and has become influential in determining access to strategic positions in government, the basic necessities of life, and indeed survival in certain habitats, bringing about division in the country and threatening national integration. Directors (leadership) of religious affairs turn blind eyes and deaf ears when juicy appointments favour their followers, even if undeserved. Rather than tolerance, intolerance has become the order of the day. Religious intolerance is seen as "hostility towards other religions as well as the inability of religious adherents to harmonise between the theories and practical aspects of religion." Obviously, the interpretation of religious thoughts and their translation into behaviours or acts that feature in the everyday lives of individuals pose a problem to adherents. Furthermore, the diverging interpretations of doctrines within the same religion create mutually intolerant interpretations that birth different levels of fanaticism in adherents¹⁹. This creates a scene in which different directors (leaderships) interpret the same script while instilling their respective worldviews in the actors under their tutelage. The performances of these actors can only be conflicting, confusing, and misleading to the audience.

Religious Leaders as Principal Actors in Nigeria's Socio-political Stage

The role of leadership in the attainment of both personal and societal goals cannot be overstated. Leadership in a society is like the icing needed to beautify the collection of personal and collective capabilities knitted together to make a society functional. More often than not, leadership tends to be conceived of as a positive exercise where individual or group talents are harnessed for the common good or benefit. However, leadership could take on an entirely counterproductive outlook, which is rarely analyzed but has been captured in the toxic triangle analysis²⁰. The toxic triangle describes a fusion of leader, follower, and environmental contexts that support the thriving of destructive leadership. A diagrammatic presentation of the toxic triangle is shown below.

Figure 1: The toxic triangle: elements in three domains related to destructive leadership

Charisma is identified as one of the key characteristics of destructive leaders in the domain of destructive leaders. Though not all charismatic leaders are destructive, charismatic leaders could be dangerous because they are prone to using power for self-serving purposes. Most charismatic leaders articulate compelling visionary calculations, possess self-presentation skills, and possess personal energy that sweep the masses off their feet and enhance their grip on the latter's psyche. More so, charismatic leaders tend to be preoccupied with building support for themselves rather than pro-social ideals. Hence, most destructive leaders are charismatic, but not all charismatic leaders are destructive. Destructive leaders also exercise power in personalized ways that dehumanize their subordinates while imposing their goals on followers through subtle coercion or aggressive ways.

Closely linked to charisma and the personalized use of power is narcissism, which involves having an exaggerated sense of self-worth accompanied by the expectation of unquestioning compliance and entitlement to favours from followers or other people. Narcissistic people also exhibit sadistic tendencies and claim special knowledge in all areas. Susceptible followership, though rarely talked about in discourses on leadership, provides a very strong base for the success or failure of any leadership.²¹ Identified two types of followers' support for destructive leadership. There are those who, because of unmet needs and immaturity, passively allow bad leaders to assume power. Colluders support destructive leaders because they want to promote themselves in an enterprise consistent with their worldview. Complicit followership is described as worse than incompetent leadership²². Hence, true followers ought to constitute a court for leadership, serving as watchdogs to checkmate, compel, suggest, and even confront those contracted to rule. Effective followers have the courage to accept responsibility, question an office, take part in change, serve the needs of the organization, and relinquish membership when necessary.²³

Conducive environments with features of instability, perceived threat, cultural values, and the absence of checks and balances support the emergence of destructive leaders. When people feel their survival is threatened in the face of an already unstable socio-political and economic environment, their hearts are tuned to accept assertive leadership that promises some ray of hope, whereas the leadership perpetuates the perception of threat to motivate followers. Though the toxic triangle of destructive leadership portrays secular leadership, its tenets depict to a large extent the nature of religious operations in Nigeria. Elements of the destructive leader, such as charisma, personalized power, and hate ideology, characterize many religious leaders in Nigeria. Little wonder: the nation is described as the most religious, yet the milieu stinks of hate and all forms of anomalies that should characterise an intellectually backward and spiritually or morally bankrupt society.

The Way Forward

Religious leaders must learn to detect antagonism towards other faiths in their members at the formative stage before it escalates into a behaviour that would be difficult to uproot or purge, thereby predisposing adherents to violent encounters that would attract international attention. Secondly, dialogue should involve followers of major religious groups with commitments to peaceful co-existence and be conducted in moments of "peace" or "relative calm," not after violent clashes when promises or resolutions are overly emotionally charged and most likely impracticable or just entertaining to the audience.

Also, religious leaders ought to be held responsible for the misbehaviour of their followers since, to a large extent, leaders influence the thought patterns, behaviors, and lifestyles of the latter. Most, if not all are aware of the perception and level of devotion accorded them by their followers. The need for transparency and synergy between what is contained in writing in holy books, documents of commitment to peaceful coexistence, utterances and practical behaviours cannot be overstated because, the innate predisposition to distrust the intentions of the other in social interaction is rooted in the consciousness of many. To overcome this is to see actions/behaviours matching words in speech and writing. Search for truth should be an exercise engaged in by both religious leaders and followers so that an overriding of the latter by the former can be put in check, this is not to however, derision or denigrate the place of religious leaders in religious practice.

Endnotes

¹Chukwuka H. Achunike, "Religious Practices in Nigeria as Source of Social Conflict," *Journal of Liberal Studies*. 12 Vol. 1&2, (2008), 28.

²Austin Cline. *Religious References on the Definition of Religion*. <https://www.learnreligions.com/defining-reeligion-250676>. Accessed February 16, 2019.

³Ibid.

⁴Jonah I. Elaigwu "The Management of Ethno-religious Conflict in Northern Nigeria: Towards a more peaceful and Harmonious Geopolity," (2004) presented at the Northern Governor's Peace Conference, Kaduna, 1st – 2nd Dec. 2004.

⁵Achunike, 28.

⁶Cornelius A. Omonokhua, *Religion and Politics in Nigeria* (2018). <https://www.pressreader.com/Nigeria/daily-trust-Sunday/20181209/282114932656197>. Accessed February 16, 2019.

⁷Kimberly Moffitt Dramaturgical Analysis in Sociology: Definition and Examples (2015) <https://study.com/academy/lesson/dramaturgical-analysis-in-society-definition-examples-quiz.html> Accessed January 22, 2019.

⁸Literary Devices Editors. Metaphor. (2013) <http://Literarydevices.Net/Metaphor/> Accessed February 4, 2019.

⁹Nikki L. Cole, *Goffman's Front Stage and Back Stage Behaviour*. (2018) <https://www.thoughtco.com/goffmans-front-stage-and-back-stage-behavior-4087971> Accessed on January 22, 2019.

¹⁰Peter Kivisto and Dan Pittman, *Goffman's Dramaturgical Sociology*. (2007) <https://sk.sagepub.com/books/illuminating-social-life-6e/nl3.ml> Accessed January 22, 2019.

¹¹Joseph. O. Charles. *Sociological Theory: A Historical Approach on Man and Society*. 3rd ed. (Nigeria: University of Calabar Press, 2014), 196.

¹²Ibid, 196.

¹³Ibid, 198.

¹⁴Ashley R. Norris, "Impression Management: Considering Cultural, Social and Spiritual Factors". *Inquires Journal/ Student Pulse*, 3(07), 2011 <http://www.inquiresjournal.com/amp/553/iimpression-management-considering-cultural-social-and-spiritual-factors>

¹⁵Charles, “Sociological Theory”, 202.

¹⁶Ibid, 202.

¹⁷Chattam House. *Collective Action on Corruption in Nigeria*. (2021) <https://www.chattamhouse.org/2021/03/collective-action-corruption-nigeria/context-religion-nigeria>

¹⁸Mike Haralambos and Martins Holborn, *Sociology Themes and Perspectives*. 5th ed. (London: Harper-Collins Publishers, 2000), 435.

¹⁹Rotgak I. Gofwen, *Religious Conflicts in Northern Nigeria and Nation Building: The Throes of two Decades 1980-2000* (Nigeria: Human Rights Monitor, 2004), 51.

²⁰Art Padilla, Robert Hogan and Robert B. Kaiser, “The Toxic Triangle: Destructive Leaders, Susceptible Followers and Conducive environments” In *The Leadership Quarterly* 18.3 (2007), DOI: 10.1016/j.leaqua.2007.03.00, 176-194.

²¹Ibid.

²²OluFasan, “Nigerians are Culpable for the Utter Misrule of their Country”. (2020), <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2020/02/Nigerians-are-culpable-for-the-utter-misrule-of-their-country/amp/> Accessed on April 10, 2020.

²³Lawrence Suda, “In Praise of Followers”. Paper presented at PMI® Global Congress 2013—North America, New Orleans, L A. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute, 29, Oct. 2013 <https://www.pmi.org/learning/library/importance-of-effective-followers-5887>

